

STRESS-STRAIN STATE INVESTIGATION OF ADHESIVE LAYER IN SANDWICH STRUCTURE OF FLYING VEHICLE

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SUMMARY: The studies of theoretical modeling of sandwich shell (SS) and experimental sandwich beam (SB) are presented in this paper. The displacements of adhesive layers are computed in the whole SS. The Hamilton's principle is used to derive the equations of equilibrium, which contains 6 differential equations with 16 orders.

The high temperature foil strain gauges (KFH-5-c1-11) are embedded in the adhesive layers on experimental approach. The strain gauges FLA-5-11 are attached on the outer surface of facing sheets. The test of SB is carried out by Material Test System with 3-points and 4-points bending conditions. The experimental results show the effect of adhesive layers on the whole SB.

KEYWORDS: adhesive layer, core, facing sheet, stress-strain state, deterioration and embedded strain gauge.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structure has high bending stiffness characteristics with little resultant weight penalty. That is why sandwich panels and shells have widely been used in aerospace, shipbuilding and other industries. Experimental investigation and testing of sandwich structure reveal that structural deterioration begins at different places for the two construction methods. In glued structures deterioration starts at the interface between the core and the facing. For brazed structures the core material closest to the brazing deteriorates first. This rises interest in investigation of adhesive layer to know the theoretical and experimental stress-strain distribution of adhesive layers under particular load conditions.

HYPOTHESIS OF MODELING

The present study focuses on sandwich structure applied to flying vehicle.

So we assume

- the thickness of facing sheets and adhesive layers are much smaller than that of core;
- the core is treated as orthotropic body, which can resist longitudinal and transversal forces;
- the adhesive layers behave as isotropic material and resist only transversal forces;
- the facing faces operate according to the KIRCHHOFF-LOVE hypothesis, i.e.

$$\varepsilon_z = \gamma_{xz} = \gamma_{yz} = 0$$

METHOD OF FORMULATION OF GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Assumptions for displacements

The solutions for the displacements of core and facings are expressed as following:

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= A_i(x, y) + B_i(x, y)z \\ v_i &= C_i(x, y) + D_i(x, y)z \quad i = 3, 4, 5 \\ w_i &= E_i(x, y) + F_i(x, y)z \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where 3 designates core

4,5 designate adhesive layers.

Then $A_i, B_i, C_i, D_i, E_i, F_i$ can be obtained by continuity conditions among each layers.

Continuity conditions on the surfaces

At the core:

$$\begin{aligned} u_3 &= u_5, \quad v_3 = v_5, \quad w_3 = w_5 \quad \text{as } z = \frac{h}{2}; \\ u_3 &= u_4, \quad v_3 = v_4, \quad w_3 = w_4 \quad \text{as } z = -\frac{h}{2}; \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where h is the thickness of core.

At the 4th layer (adhesive layer):

$$\begin{aligned} u_4 &= u_3 + \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial w_3}{\partial x}, \quad v_4 = v_3 + \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial w_3}{\partial y}, \quad w_4 = w_3 \quad \text{as } z = -\frac{h}{2}; \\ u_4 &= u_1 - \frac{t_1}{2} \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x}, \quad v_4 = v_1 - \frac{t_1}{2} \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y}, \quad w_4 = w_1 \quad \text{as } z = -\frac{h}{2} - \delta; \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where subscript 1 denotes the lower facing sheet (1st layer),

t_1 is the thickness of 1st layer, and δ is the thickness of adhesive layers.

At the 5th layer (adhesive layer):

$$\begin{aligned} u_5 &= u_3 - \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial w_3}{\partial x}, \quad v_5 = v_3 - \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial w_3}{\partial y}, \quad w_5 = w_3 \quad \text{as } z = \frac{h}{2}; \\ u_5 &= u_2 + \frac{t_2}{2} \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial x}, \quad v_5 = v_2 + \frac{t_2}{2} \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial y}, \quad w_5 = w_2 \quad \text{as } z = \frac{h}{2} + \delta; \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where subscript 2 denotes the upper facing sheet (2nd layer),

t_2 is the thickness of 2nd layer, and δ is the thickness of adhesive layers.

Displacement of each layer

As the coefficients in Equation (1) are derived by continuity conditions, the displacements of core and adhesive layers can be expressed by that of facing sheets:

$$u_3 = \frac{1}{2}u_1 + \frac{1}{2}u_2 + \left[-\frac{t_1}{4} - \frac{h\delta z}{4(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\right] \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} + \left[\frac{t_2}{4} - \frac{h\delta z}{4(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\right] \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

$$v_3 = \frac{1}{2}v_1 + \frac{1}{2}v_2 + \left[-\frac{t_1}{4} - \frac{h\delta z}{4(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\right] \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} + \left[\frac{t_2}{4} - \frac{h\delta z}{4(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\right] \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial y} \quad (6)$$

$$w_3 = \frac{1}{2}w_1 + \frac{1}{2}w_2 \quad (7)$$

$$u_4 = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{h}{4\delta} - \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)u_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{h}{4\delta} + \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)u_2 - \left[\frac{t_1}{4}\left(1 - \frac{h}{2\delta} - \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} + z + 2\frac{\delta z}{h} + \frac{hz}{2\delta}\right) - \frac{z^2}{\delta} - 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right] \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} - \left[\frac{t_2}{4}\left(1 + \frac{h}{2\delta} + \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} + z + 2\frac{\delta z}{h} + \frac{hz}{2\delta} - \frac{z^2}{\delta} - 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right)\right] \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial x} \quad (8)$$

$$v_4 = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{h}{4\delta} - \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)v_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{h}{4\delta} + \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)v_2 - \left[\frac{t_1}{4}\left(1 - \frac{h}{2\delta} - \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} + z + 2\frac{\delta z}{h} + \frac{hz}{2\delta}\right) - \frac{z^2}{\delta} - 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right] \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} - \left[\frac{t_2}{4}\left(1 + \frac{h}{2\delta} + \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} + z + 2\frac{\delta z}{h} + \frac{hz}{2\delta} - \frac{z^2}{\delta} - 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right)\right] \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial y} \quad (9)$$

$$w_4 = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{h}{4\delta} - \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)w_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{h}{4\delta} + \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)w_2 \quad (10)$$

$$u_5 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{h}{4\delta} - \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)u_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{h}{4\delta} + \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)u_2 + \left[-\frac{t_1}{4}\left(1 + \frac{h}{2\delta} - \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} - z - 2\frac{\delta z}{h} - \frac{hz}{2\delta}\right) - \frac{z^2}{\delta} + 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right] \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} + \left[-\frac{t_2}{4}\left(-1 + \frac{h}{2\delta} - \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} - z - 2\frac{\delta z}{h} - \frac{hz}{2\delta} - \frac{z^2}{\delta} + 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right)\right] \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial x} \quad (11)$$

$$v_5 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{h}{4\delta} - \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)v_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{h}{4\delta} + \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)v_2 + \left[-\frac{t_1}{4}\left(1 + \frac{h}{2\delta} - \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} - z - 2\frac{\delta z}{h} - \frac{hz}{2\delta}\right) - \frac{z^2}{\delta} + 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right] \frac{\partial w_1}{\partial y} + \left[-\frac{t_2}{4}\left(-1 + \frac{h}{2\delta} - \frac{z}{\delta}\right) + \frac{h^2}{8(z^2 - \frac{h^2}{4})}\left(\frac{h}{2} + \frac{h^2}{4\delta} - z - 2\frac{\delta z}{h} - \frac{hz}{2\delta} - \frac{z^2}{\delta} + 2\frac{z^3}{\delta h}\right)\right] \frac{\partial w_2}{\partial y} \quad (12)$$

$$w_5 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{h}{4\delta} - \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)w_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{h}{4\delta} + \frac{z}{2\delta}\right)w_2 \quad (13)$$

Variation integral for the sandwich cylindrical shell

The strain energy can be achieved by the displacements of each layer. Then we apply HAMILTON's principle to derive the equations of equilibrium expressed by displacements of facing sheets ($u_i, v_i, w_i, i=1,2$, where 1 denotes 1st face and 2 denotes 2nd face.)

SYSTEM OF EQUATIONS OF EQUILIBRIUM

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(-J_1 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_3)u_1 + (-J_4 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_5 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} - J_3)u_2 + (J_6 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})v_1 - (J_7 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})v_2 + \\
 &+ (J_8 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} - J_9 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} + J_{10} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})w_1 + (-J_{11} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} - J_{12} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} + J_{13} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})w_2 = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(-J_4 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_5 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} - J_3)u_1 + (-J_{14} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_{15} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_3)u_2 - (J_7 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})v_1 + (J_{16} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})v_2 + \\
 &+ (J_8 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} - J_{17} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} - J_{18} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})w_1 + (-J_{11} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} - J_{19} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} - J_{20} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})w_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(J_6 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})u_1 - (J_7 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})u_2 + (-J_{21} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_{22} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{23})v_1 + (-J_{24} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_{25} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{26})v_2 + \\
 &+ (J_{27} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} + J_{28} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} + J_{29} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})w_1 + (-J_{30} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} - J_{31} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} + J_{32} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})w_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(-J_7 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})u_1 + (J_{16} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta})u_2 + (-J_{24} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_{25} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{26})v_1 + (-J_{33} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} - J_{34} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{35})v_2 + \\
 &+ (J_{27} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} - J_{36} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} + J_{37} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})w_1 + (-J_{30} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} + J_{38} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} + J_{39} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})w_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(-J_8 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} + J_9 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} - J_{10} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})u_1 + (-J_8 \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} + J_{17} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} + J_{18} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})u_2 + (-J_{27} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} - J_{28} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} - J_{29} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})v_1 \\
 &+ (-J_{27} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} + J_{36} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} - J_{37} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})v_2 + (J_{40} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^4} + J_{41} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \beta^4} + J_{42} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta^2} + J_{43} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + J_{44} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{45})w_1 \\
 &+ (J_{46} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^4} + J_{47} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \beta^4} + J_{48} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta^2} + J_{49} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + J_{50} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{51})w_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(J_{11} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} + J_{12} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} - J_{13} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})u_1 + (J_{11} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^3} + J_{19} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta^2} + J_{20} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha})u_2 + (J_{30} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} + J_{31} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} - J_{32} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})v_1 \\
 &+ (J_{30} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \beta^3} - J_{38} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta} - J_{39} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta})v_2 + (J_{46} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^4} + J_{47} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \beta^4} + J_{48} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta^2} + J_{49} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + J_{50} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{51})w_1 \\
 &+ (J_{52} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^4} + J_{53} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \beta^4} + J_{54} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta^2} + J_{55} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + J_{56} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + J_{57})w_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

where J_i are integral constants composed of elastic and geometric parameters, and α, β are coordinates on the middle surface of cylindrical shell. Since we achieved 6 differential equations with 16 orders, we can find the solutions of these differential equations by substituting boundary conditions. Once the displacements of facing sheets are obtained the displacements of adhesive layers and core also can be achieved through Equations (5)-(13). Then the mathematical model of adhesive layers of sandwich cylindrical shell can be established.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF SANDWICH BEAM

Test specimens

The present experimental study focuses on sandwich beam applied to flying vehicle. So we choose the facing sheets (titanium alloy plate with thickness 1.6mm) and adhesive film (FM73, products of Cyanamid) with thickness much smaller than that of core (MIL-C-7438 with thickness 3.8mm, products of Alcore). The geometry for the test specimen is shown in Fig.1

Fig.1. Test specimen geometry of sandwich beam

Specimen manufacture

The high temperature foil strain gauges (KFH-5-c1-11) with high temperature lead wires (L-1) were embedded in adhesive layers, and settled at 100 mm apart from mid-span. Strain gauges (FLA-5-11) were adhered on the outer surfaces of facing sheets, and located at 100 mm away from mid-span. Then, the whole sandwich beam was cured in the autoclave (heated up in 60 minutes to 120°C , hold 60 minutes at 120°C and 40 psi).

Experimental procedure

The specimens were tested in the Material Test System (MTS 810) which is a closed loop series with a load capacity of 100kN. The loads applied to the specimen are 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450 and 500 kg with 3-points and 4-points bending conditions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The strain distribution of adhesive layers and facing sheets under different loading conditions are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3.

Fig.2. 3-points bending strain distribution

Fig.3. 4-points bending strain distribution

Some results can be observed according to the previous experimental figures:

1. *The strain of the upper face is the same as that of lower face on the same cross section, for the sandwich beam is symmetrical.*
2. *The effect of adhesive layer to the whole sandwich beam is obvious. If the adhesive layer is not counted, the strain distribution along the cross section will be linear. But experimental results reveal that there is a strain twisted point between facing sheet and core (i.e. the adhesive layer). It means the effect of adhesive in glued sandwich structure need be considered in theoretical and in experimental investigations.*
3. *The strain difference between face and adhesive layer of upper part is much bigger than that of lower part of sandwich beam. Because the strain gauges on the upper part are nearer the loading point than that of lower part away from the support point.*

CONCLUSIONS

The mathematical stress-strain state model of sandwich shell with calculating adhesive layer is presented. The displacement functions of each layer are achieved by continuity conditions. The HAMILTON'S principle is applied to derive the equations of equilibrium expressed by displacements of facing sheets. System of differential equations with 16 orders is obtained. Then the solutions of these differential equations can be found by substituting boundary conditions.

The experimental approach of strain measurement of adhesive layer is shown in this paper. The high temperature foil strain gauges with high temperature lead wires were embedded in adhesive layers. The testing was carried out in the MTS 810 with different loading conditions. The experimental result revealed the effect and behavior of adhesive layer in symmetrical sandwich beam.

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